

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' ARTISTIC LITERACY SKILLS IN EXTRA-CURRICULUM ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *In this article, today's state education standards are based on the competence approach, that is, the personality of each student. The student's personality develops during the educational process. Fine art is the oldest of the arts. Humanity appeared to paint. Through images, they express their dreams and thoughts. A clear example of this is the masterpieces of art found on Sarmishsay rocks and many other places.*

Keywords: *different patterns made of plaster, school of Fine Arts, reciprocity in Painting, symmetrical pieces, aesthetic education, artistic taste and creative ability, skills and competencies in real painting, theoretical foundations of art, compositional solution in painting, painter pedagogic training, geometric objects, describing the drawing of sockets...*

Fine art is the oldest of the arts. Humanity appeared to paint. Through images, they express their dreams and thoughts. A clear example of this is the masterpieces of art found on Sarmishsay rocks and many other places. In addition, we know from history that during the period of Amir Temur, the attention to visual arts was extremely high, and the Samarkand school of visual arts had its influence on the culture of the peoples of the world.

The famous pedagogue-artist N.N.Ge said: "Always remember this law: To describe is to see proportions, so never see or describe parts separately. You need to describe not just one eye, one ear or one eyebrow, but how these parts are located on the face and how they are proportional to each other. When describing these parts, always see them as a whole: always describe the symmetrical parts together and at the same time, both ears, both eyes [1], both cheeks..."

The school teacher has the task of developing the aesthetic education, artistic taste and creative abilities of students, providing them with a deep understanding of the fundamentals of fine art in order to describe the existence, and the formation of skills and qualifications for real painting. Solving this task can be solved only by the student's acquisition of the skills of visual description, perception of existence, formation of hand, mind and sense organs. An art teacher should master not only the practical knowledge of fine art, but also the theoretical foundations of fine art. Because Leonardo da Vinci, the world-recognized great artist and unique engineer who left behind his immortal works, "People who love practice without science are like geniuses who set out to swim without a rudder or a compass, because they never know where they are going. "For this reason, first learn the science, and then turn to the practice born from this science."

For this reason, we paid attention to the theoretical foundations of visual art before describing it in scientific work. This is mainly reflected in such topics as compositional solution, linear - basic structure, proportions, light-shadow laws, sequence of work.

It is known that in the process of training an artist, an artist-pedagogue, an important place is occupied by educational tasks such as the drawing of geometric objects, their collection, various patterns made of plaster, and the drawing of sockets. The above-mentioned topics are very useful

for future teachers, no matter what type of visual arts they work in, or in their pedagogical activities.

Depicting a person, looking carefully at the human images in various thematic paintings, we can be sure that the anatomical and plastic solutions in them are a true representation of their constructive and basic structures. All of these indicate that the artist has mastered the basics of fine art.

After studying anatomical models made of plaster based on human representation, details of the head, eyes, ears, nose, mouth, paws, heels, etc., among the bright examples of ancient sculpture, David, Goodon model, Plaster models of Antinous, Diadumenes, Socrates, Gattamelatta, Voltaire, and others proceed to be painted. All of the above serve as one of the primary sources for describing a living person.

It is for this reason that teaching the painting system for several centuries begins with teaching the basics of perspective and light and shade in depicting a work. Drawing is the mastery of the unique features and characteristic image of the object by seeing it in various changes depending on the environment. Seeing the highest peaks of fine art, learning to progress - creating an image, starting with painting. Painting is not only for artists who are an important basis of activity, but also the volumetric aspects of any image, the interaction of the elements participating in it, their proportions, the expression of movement, the general composition of texture are brought to a specific solution. The sense of feeling the spatial aspects of the existence that surrounds us also embodies an emotional content that is clear in its nature. A full sense of spatial space has a positive effect on a person. Often, a wide open spatial space evokes a feeling of freedom, joy and excitement in our body, and vice versa. Any image on a flat surface has spatial properties to one degree or another. For this reason, in the process of creating an artistic image, the problem of organizing spatiality in this image lies before every artist who creates an image. In order to solve this problem correctly, we will also touch upon the laws of perspective. When it comes to the role of composition in the image, first of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to its basic laws. Along with the basic laws of composition, there are its rules and methods that are important in revealing the pictorial "essence" of the plot, and they are technical tools in the organization of a plastic motif. They are aimed at the realization of new tasks faced by art, which have arisen over the years by new generations of artists and other methods and tools that meet their needs. Adherence to the general laws of composition is very important in creating a work belonging to any genre of painting, as well as theater, cinema and television. The importance of this or that rule depends on the type of art, the genre of the work, and, of course, the author's ability to use these tools effectively.

The development and implementation of the national personnel training program in our country is of great importance in the process of education. Because training of national personnel and their comprehensive development, along with training of highly qualified teachers and pedagogues, serves as the main factor for providing education to the young generation at a high level. "We consider it our first priority to improve the activities of all links of the education and training system based on the requirements of today's times [2] [3]".

Currently, in the conditions of the rapid development of science and technology, due to the fact that the intellectual circle of a person is growing extremely and scientific information is increasing, it has become extremely necessary to maintain and develop the emotional state of people towards art.

President Sh.M. Mirziyoev said, "It is clear to all of us that the cornerstone of development and the force that makes the country powerful and the nation great is science, education and upbringing. Our future, the future, the future of our country, first of all, is closely related to the education system and the education we give to our children" as well as reminding once again that education and upbringing cannot be separated from each other. We understand that education and training cannot be delayed or stopped even for a minute.

Today, it is necessary to further improve the quality of education, to use various methods in the educational process, to find new ways to educate young people in accordance with the requirements of the time. Based on the requirements, in order to regulate relations in the field of education, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "ON EDUCATION" dated September 23, 2020, No. LRU-637 generation, it is correct to consider it as another example of our country's high attention to education.

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Internet resources

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